

Optimizing Kubernetes Network Performance: A Study of Container Network Interfaces and System Tuning Profiles

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Abstract:

The rapid development of cloud computing and big data has led to containers becoming the top choice for application deployment platforms due to their lightweight and flexible nature. Deploying, maintaining, and scaling containerized applications across dispersed environments has never been easier than with Kubernetes, a top container orchestration platform. Central to Kubernetes' functionality is its networking model, which connects containerized workloads seamlessly. This study explores Kubernetes network performance, emphasizing the role of Container Network Interfaces (CNIs) like Cilium, Flannel, Calico, and Antrea. Each CNI plugin is

analyzed based on its architecture, functionality, and suitability for various application scenarios, highlighting trade-offs between simplicity, security, throughput, and scalability. Additionally, system tuning profiles and Kubernetes' default networking solutions are discussed to optimize communication between containers. The findings provide insights into selecting and configuring CNIs to enhance the performance, reliability, and security of Kubernetes clusters, offering guidance for deploying modern, network-intensive applications.

Keywords: *Kubernetes, Container Network Interfaces, Network Performance Optimization, System Tuning Profiles, Cluster Scalability, Network Security.*

Introduction

The open-source container orchestration technology Kubernetes was developed by Google in 2014, building upon their earlier systems, Borg and Omega (Verma, Aet al., 2015). Numerous duties that are typically performed by system administrators are automated by Kubernetes, such as centralized logging, monitoring, failover protocols, and infrastructure optimization (Burns, et al., 2016). Kubernetes' core capabilities, such as auto-scaling and load balancing, are further improved by additional functionalities and third-party apps built using the Kubernetes API. Pods are collections of containers, and Kubernetes is a

method for managing them that takes care of deployment and resource control directly (Arora, & Tewari, 2023). Yet, in complicated designs, excessive resource utilization and worse performance could result from Kubernetes' default scheduler ignoring container coupling and dependencies (Senjab, et al., 2023; Bishukarma, 2024).

The main components of Kubernetes, which is a distributed architecture based on the master-slave model, are worker nodes, client command-line tools, and master nodes (Bauskar, 2024). In recent years, Kubernetes (K8s) has emerged as a front-runner among solutions for managing and orchestrating containerized workloads and

services in scalable and automated ways (Tran, Vu, & Kim, 2022; Gopalsamy, 2022). Kubernetes, developed by Google, has become the standard in the industry because of its solid design, scalability, and flexibility. Since the efficient management of massive clusters and resources is crucial in areas like AI and high-performance computing, it has found widespread use in these areas (Bauskar, 2022; Sinha, 2024; Sinha, 2024). The effectiveness of Kubernetes in workload orchestration is strongly influenced by the selection of container network interface (CNI) plugins to control the flow of data between nodes and pods, which in turn affects latency, bandwidth, and the overall efficiency of the network.

Improving network performance requires both choosing the right CNI and optimizing the system. Changes to kernel settings, packet size, and the Maximum Transmission Unit (MTU) may have a significant impact on CNI performance (Chandu, 2024). Optimizing for larger packet sizes improves the performance of certain CNIs, whereas smaller sizes provide better results for others (Chandu, 2022). The open-source project Kubernetes (K8s) was first created by Google and then contributed to the CNCF (Arora, & Tewari, 2022).

Kubernetes is classified as a PaaS and can be implemented on physical servers, virtual machines, and cloud environments, such as Google Cloud Platform (GCP). Among the many useful capabilities offered by Kubernetes are storage orchestration, load balancing, service discovery, self-healing, bin packing, automated deployments and rollbacks, configuration and secret management, and self-service (Bauskar, 2023; Vishwakarma, & Kumar, 2024). Kubernetes, a robust and versatile platform, has revolutionized the management and orchestration of containerized applications. Application deployment, scalability, and administration are made easier using Kubernetes (Dey, 2016). It accomplishes this by simplifying infrastructure difficulties and facilitating efficient resource management (Vishwakarma, & Suyambu, 2024; Darchiashvili, et al., 2024). The premier alternative for managing containerized workloads in cloud-native environments, it has

received great recognition for its outstanding stability, scalability, and fault tolerance. Kubernetes makes it easier to build applications as networks of separate but linked services, which in turn simplifies their development and scalability. native apps for the cloud (Brewer, 2015; Arora, & Tewari, 2022).

Motivation

As Kubernetes continues to dominate the landscape of container orchestration, its network performance becomes a critical factor for ensuring the efficiency, scalability, and reliability of modern applications. However, the diverse choices of Container Network Interfaces (CNIs) and the lack of a clear understanding of their performance trade-offs pose challenges for system administrators and developers. Additionally, optimizing system tuning profiles for different workloads remains underexplored, leaving opportunities for significant performance gains untapped. This research goal is to fill these gaps by providing a systematic evaluation and practical guidelines for optimizing Kubernetes network performance.

The following paper is organized as: Section II provide the Kubernetes Networking overview, Section III discussed the Kubernetes Network Performance of CNIS, Section IV give the Kubernetes and Its CNI Plugin Support for System Tuning Profiles, Section V provide the Kubernetes Network Policies, Section VI give the Literature Review and last section VII provide the Conclusion and Future Work.

Kubernetes Networking: An Overview

Google first suggested Kubernetes in 2015 as a framework for orchestrating containers, which could run applications across several host servers (Burns, et al., 2016). Kubernetes, which is based on container technology, streamlines the process of managing cross-host containerized applications with basic features like elastic scaling, service discovery, high availability, and resource scheduling (Mondal, et al., 2022; Bishukarma, 2023). It offers better management tools to help with things like development, deployment, and monitoring operations.

Automated administration of multiplatform transplanting, application development, and other activities are all within its capabilities.

Kubernetes Architecture

The primary components of the Kubernetes distributed architecture are client command-line tools, worker (node) nodes, and master nodes. Figure 1 depicts the Kubernetes diagram's particular architecture.

Figure 1. Kubernetes Architecture

Master Node

Every Kubernetes cluster relies on its master node, the central control node that handles application administration, resource scheduling, and task allocation. Most notably, master nodes include API Server, ETCD, Schedule, and Controller Manager (Bernstein, 2014). Then, giving a quick example of them as follows (Merkel, 2014):

- The API Server forms connections between the different parts of the Kubernetes cluster, executes actions on each item in the cluster, and offers services like adding, removing, modifying, and querying resource objects (Goyal, 2022).
- The Kubernetes cluster's administrator and nerve center is Controller Manager. Timely detection and handling of abnormalities in the system are responsibilities of the Controller Manager (Goyal, 2021).

- The Kubernetes cluster uses Scheduler as its default resource scheduler. In accordance with the anticipated policies, the scheduler assigns pending pods to the anticipated nodes (Goyal, 2023). Scheduler receives the newly created Pod object from the Controller Manager, finds an appropriate node schedule for it, and then, via the API Server, uploads the binding information to ETCD.

- The Kubernetes cluster relies on ETCD, a key-value store that ensures its steady operation and provides high availability and durability for storing different types of cluster data.

Worker Node

The Kubernetes cluster's worker node is responsible for consuming resources, carrying out duties given to it by the master node, and receiving and completing tasks under the master's supervision (Bentaleb, et al., 2022;

Thomas, et al., 2024). The two primary components of a worker node are:

- Kubelet service processes control the container life cycle, perform tasks supplied by the master node, and operate on every node in the cluster. In addition, kubelet monitors the nodes' condition and communicates real-time information on the operational status and resource utilization of all worker nodes to the master control node.
- The Kube-proxy service process executes on every worker node and sends the backend the access request that the service has received.

Kubernetes Components

Utilizing the Kubectl tool, users have the ability to manipulate resource objects, including Pod, Label, Replication Controller, Replica-Set, Deployment, and Service. The outcomes of these operations may then be permanently stored in ETCD. Briefly illustrating them here:

- **Pods** are the fundamental building block of Kubernetes scheduling. A "root container" for pausing is included in every pod, along with the user's business container. A user's business containers that are directly associated with their company are also included in each pod.
- **Labels** in Kubernetes are represented as a key-value pair. In a key-value pair, the user must provide both the key and the value. The label allows users to conduct multi-dimensional resource management. The Kubernetes system relies on Replication Controller, among other essential components. It can handle a bunch of Pods listed in the YAML file, making sure that the number of copies of the application Pods stays within the user-specified range while it runs its life cycle.
- **Replica-Set** aids in keeping an eye on every pod. Replica-Set specifically helps Deployment maintain pod availability at a certain level.
- **Replica-Set** and pod management is aided by deployment. Furthermore, it is utilized for the purpose of rolling updates when

applications inside Pods need upgrades. In addition, the HPA is a useful tool for auto-scaling pods (Bishukarma, 2023). Among Kubernetes's many useful features, autoscaling stands out. It enables the autonomous and flexible operation of containerized applications and services.

- **Service** may provide a shared IP address to a collection of containers that share a similar purpose and distribute loading responsibilities to each container individually. The service establishes a connection to the backend Pod copies using the label selector when the client uses the address it gave to request access to a group of Pod copies.
- **Ingress** facilitates the binding of requests to the Services, which is particularly useful for demands of a large scale. Load balancing is another feature it offers. In most cases, for inbound requests to be routed to the correct endpoint, an Ingress controller must be present in the cluster.

Kubernetes Network Performance of Container Network Interfaces (Cnis)

VFs are transferred from the node's namespace to the pod's namespace at the pod's startup using CNI. For each node, CNI returns VFs to its namespace once the pod shuts down. Because it can only add one VF to a pod's network namespace, irrespective of the pod's needs, the CNI originally came from Mellanox CNI [32]. The following CNIS are covered in this section:

Flannel

Kubernetes Flannel is an easy-to-use and customizable CNI plugin for creating flat networks in Kubernetes clusters. Encapsulation using VXLAN is the main technique used to manage overlay networks, which ensures that pods on different nodes may communicate without any problems. Novianti, & Basuki, (2021) tested Flannel's performance and found that it achieved a respectable throughput, albeit it lagged behind competing CNIs as Kube-Router. The simplicity of flannel's design is both its strength and its weakness. Its little setup

requirements and ease of deployment are two of its beneficial aspects. On the other hand, it could need assistance in order to manage other features offered by other CNIs, such as traffic segmentation and network regulations. However, Flannel is still the go-to for small to medium clusters that value simplicity, convenience of setup, and operation above all else. Qi, et al., (2021) and Bishukarma, (2023) highlighted that, particularly in workloads that are heavy on networks, Flannel's performance may be improved by practical tweaking. Zeng, et

al., (2017) found that Flannel's performance presents a nice balance between simplicity and functionality, making it suitable for many ordinary Kubernetes installations, while it's not the best. Larsson, et al., (2020) emphasized the significance of considering fundamental infrastructure components such as etcd when assessing the efficiency of Kubernetes networking solutions, including Flannel. Figure 2 shows the Flannel CNI-based networking with VXLAN tunnelling (Scano, et al., 2023).

Figure 2. Networking Based on Flannel CNI Using the VXLAN Tunnelling

Cilium

Cilium is a powerful Kubernetes CNI plugin that provides safe and efficient networking via the usage of eBPF or extended Berkeley Packet Filter. Essential for security and performance monitoring, this system is designed to handle complex network rules and provide full visibility into network traffic (Gopalsamy, et al., 2022; Gopalsamy, 2021). Novianti, & Basuki, (2021) included Cilium in a performance evaluation. Cilium may not have achieved the greatest throughput, but it is the ideal choice for scenarios requiring stringent security due to its extensive feature set and robust security capabilities (Bishukarma, 2021). In their study,

Qi, Kulkarni, and Ramakrishnan (2021) featured Cilium's advanced features, such as its seamless integration with Kubernetes and its ability to enforce network policies and provide observability. Because it uses eBPF to efficiently handle network traffic without charging more, Cilium is perfect for applications that need high performance (Bishukarma, 2022; Thomas, Vedi, & Gupta, 2021). Additionally, Cilium provides sophisticated security features like smooth encryption and accurate network management, which are very helpful to businesses looking to safeguard their microservices systems. Budigiri, et al. (2021) confirmed the same findings, indicating that systems based on eBPF, like

Cilium, may provide strong security measures without compromising performance. The

cilium's structural organization is seen in Figure 3 (Nechipurenko, 2020).

Figure 3. The Structural Organisation of the Cilium

Calico

The viral CNI plugin Calico is well-known for its scalable nature and strict enforcement of network policies. It provides options for both encapsulated and unencapsulated networking, as well as Layer 3 networking with Kubernetes. Their performance test highlighted Calico's balanced throughput and resource utilization, and they included it in their calculations (Novianti, & Basuki, 2021). In their study, Qi, Kulkarni, & Ramakrishnan, (2021) investigated how well Calico enforces security requirements and how flexible it is in meeting the needs of various networking scenarios (Thomas, 2022; Thomas, Vedi, & Gupta, 2024). Calico's ability to handle a large number of network rules

without a noticeable drop in performance is down to its architectural design, which allows it to grow horizontally (Arora, et al., 2022; Arora, Gera, & Saxena, 2021). This option is versatile since it can function in both cloud and on-premises environments and is compatible with Kubernetes network restrictions (Awaji, et al., 2024). The use of complex routing capabilities, which might be crucial in certain deployment scenarios, is also made possible by Calico's integration of BGP (Border Gateway Protocol). Nagendra, & Hemavathy, (2023) found that Calico outperforms the other CNIs that were evaluated, making it a top pick for scenarios involving high-performance networks.

Antrea

To enhance the speed and security of cluster networks, Kubernetes users may install the Antrea CNI plugin. In order to achieve high performance and enforce network regulations, it makes use of Open vSwitch (OVS). Complex features like observability, traffic engineering, and network policy are all within Antrea's capabilities. These traits are essential for efficiently handling complex network requirements in systems that are native to the cloud (Arora, Kumar, & Soni, 2024; Patel, 2024). Novianti and Basuki tested Antrea and other CNIs, such as Flannel, Calico, and Cilium, to see how well they used resources and how well they performed. The analysis highlighted that the best throughput was achieved with Kube-Router. On the other hand, Antrea' is a dependable choice for settings requiring safe and scalable network solutions due to its design, which works flawlessly with Kubernetes networking models. In addition, Qi, Kulkarni, & Ramakrishnan, (2021) noticed that Antrea's use of Open v-Switch (OVS) provides flexibility and efficiency in managing network rules and traffic streams, which is crucial for modern microservices designs. Applications that need rapid data throughput and low latency are ideal for this plugin since it utilizes hardware offloading capabilities to increase their performance. Budigiri, et al. (2021) brought to light the need to incorporate security measures into Kubernetes systems while keeping performance to a minimum. These parameters are well-suited to Antrea's attributes. The Jain, et al. (2021) benefit of adjustable data plane implementations, which are essential to Antrea's design, were also investigated.

Kubernetes and Its CNI Plugin Support System Tuning Profiles

K8s manages containerized workloads and services. Applications are scaled up and down, updated, rolled back, self-healed, etc. K8s deploy pods of containers with shared storage and network. Pod containers connect via shared

memory or localhost and have an IP address. K8s' default container engine is Docker, although its networking is different. Each K8s pod has its own IP address, thus users don't need to map ports (Arora, Khare, & Gupta, 2024). K8s networking treats pods like physical hosts in a clean, backwards-compatible manner (Rajeev Arora, 2022; Singh, Gameti, & Gupta, 2024). The dynamically created IP addresses for K8s pods are unstable. Pods are associated with a trustworthy DNS name and IP address, K8s. K8s distributes the load across the backend pods in a network. This model has these basic requirements:

- Network Address Translation (NAT) is unnecessary for container-to-container communication;
- Any two containers may communicate with any other node (and vice versa);
- Containers see the same IP as others.

Figure 4 demonstrates how the CNI plugin concept in Kubernetes makes the network address space flat and assigns control of a network segment (CIDR block) to each node. All communication between pods on the same physical node is now possible with the help of a CNI plugin that assigns each pod a globally unique virtual IP address. Flannel, Kube-router, Calico, Weave-Net, and Cilium are some of the more recent CNIs that have become trendy (Khare, Arora, & Gupta, 2024; Arora, & Khare, 2024). Current implementations of Calico and Cilium do not support the ARM architecture, which is necessary for edge deployments; hence, this article only addresses Kube-router, Flannel, and Weave-Net. CNI plugins may be included in the network and data connection layers at L2 and L3. With Kube-router and Weave-Net, Flannel is compatible with L2 (Hostgw) and L3 (VXLAN) backends. Figure 4 shows a comparison of various technologies' architectures. As a starting point for comprehending the overhead of the CNI network plugins discussed in Section III, they first present Host-mode, K8s' native networking solution, and then dive into each CNI.

Figure 4. Architecture of Kubernetes CNI

Host-Mode

With K8s' built-in networking feature, many pods may share the host's network. Because it uses host IP addresses to link containers, virtual network plugins are no longer necessary (Patel, 2021). Port issues might arise when users run several containers on a single host. In addition, containers may access the host network space in host mode, which allows pods to control and oversee the network operations of other containers.

Flannel

The most sophisticated and straightforward Kubernetes CNI. Flannel, a daemon process running on the K8s master node, configures the network and installs tunnel devices (bridge and interface) on the host machine using a distributed key-value store. Additionally, it checks for routing information (MAC, IP, VNI), maintains and distributes IP address resources for pods, and mimics the ARP protocol, filling the host ARP database (Zeng, et al., 2017). Flannel is compatible with VXLAN and Host-gw backends, allowing it to accommodate deployment requirements for diverse platforms. Flannel-IPSec, an experimental backend, encapsulates and encrypts kernel-level traffic using IP-Sec for security. VXLAN and Host-gw backends form the Flannel networking

architecture on a single host. Tunneling is used by the VXLAN backend to construct an overlay network above the underlying network. There is a virtual interface called flannel, and a network bridge called cni0 on the host machine (Chandu, 2024; Chandu, 2024). Enable communication between the VETH pair's host-end virtual interface and the flannel. At the local flannel interface, a packet is examined, among other things, to determine the physical destination IP. Then, the content is encapsulated into a separate UDP packet in kernel space using the source and destination container Ips (Singh, & Gameti, 2024). The Host-gw backend uses peer hosts as gateways to circumvent VXLAN's in-kernel packet encapsulation and decapsulation. The iptables rules of the host are immediately updated with the routing rules between the source and destination pods. All nodes must be linked to the network at layer 2 however the Host-gw backend lowers overhead.

Weave-Net

Each host's userspace has application-level virtual routers that construct the architecture of the fully emulated L2 network. Using spanning tree and gossip protocols, Weave-Net routers synchronize routing information and establish complete mesh TCP connections (Chandu, 2023; Chandu, 2024). Two encapsulation

options are available in Weave-Net: fast path and sleeve. Sleeve mode (Singh, & Gameti, 2024) entails the following steps: capturing packets from the weaving bridge (Figure 4), forwarding them to the user space virtual router for UDP encapsulation, and, lastly, sending them back to the kernel space for post-routing. Fast path mode, on the other hand, uses the Open v-Switch (OVS)'s Open-Data-Path (ODP) to encapsulate UDP packets in a VXLAN header inside kernel space, and then the virtual router uses the ODP routing tables to route the packets. It has been shown that fast route mode achieves greater performance than sleeve mode due to the reduced number of context transitions.

Kube-Router

The architecture in Figure 4 shows a minimalist but strong K8s CNI designed to simplify network fabric. Kube-router creates L3 networks by placing agents on each node. The Kube router makes use of i-BGP to share reachability and routing data between pods on the same network. The routers in a K8s cluster, which is an AS in BGP, construct a full node-to-node mesh by broadcasting the CIDR of each pod to its peers. When connecting pods on different subnets, Kube-router gives you choices like IP-in-IP tunnelling and BGP. Any IP packets sent by a pod may have their payload taken up by the host IP packets over the IP-in-IP tunnel. K8s' IPAM, pod networking, Network Policy, and other features are all interacted with via Kube-router.

Kubernetes Network Policies

While K8s's cluster-wide namespaces are useful for managing administrative and resource quotas, they aren't a foolproof method of preventing tenants from traversing the network. Despite this, major cybercrimes like the Equifax data breach have taken use of an often-mentioned high-risk vulnerability: an inadequately segmented network. By clearly outlining permitted and prohibited connections, network rules aid in providing the barriers necessary to limit traffic between pods (in

and/or across name-spaces) and between pods and remote networks (Gopalsamy, 2024; Patel, 2024). A pod-selector is used to identify which pods will be governed by a policy, and the policy itself makes up the definition of a network policy. Types that allow you to clearly define the policies, such as entrance and egress. Allowable traffic entering the target pods is defined by ingress rules, whereas permitted traffic leaving the target pods is defined by egress rules (Budigiri, et al., 2021; Patel, 2023). In each rule, you'll find a Network-Policy-Peer that lets you choose which pods on the other side of the connection can be reached and which cannot, using CIDR notation for IP address blocks, namespaces, or pod labels. Then, you'll find a Network-Policy-Port that lets you directly specify which ports or protocols can talk to the pod. If many policies choose a pod in a network, the traffic can only be limited to what is permitted by the combined entrance and egress rules of all of those policies.

CNI Plugins and Networking Modes

While K8s does not come with network policy enforcement built in, it does make use of CNI plugins. Extras, such as CNI plugins, may make use of open-source K8s components or operate as pods. Few CNI plugins enforce network restrictions as quickly as Calico and Cilium do using e-BPF, an alternative to iptables. When tested in both inter- and intra-node contexts, e-BPF outperformed iptables in terms of throughput (up 3.5 times) and latency (down 0.8 times).

Figure 5. Latency of Calico vs Cilium

Figure 5 illustrates the latency performance of Calico and Cilium in both intra-node and inter-node communication scenarios. The results show that Cilium consistently outperforms Calico in both scenarios, with significantly lower latency for intra-node communication. Cilium's intra-node latency is even comparable to host-to-host communication, highlighting its efficiency within a single node. While both solutions exhibit higher latency for inter-node communication, Cilium maintains a clear advantage over Calico in this scenario as well.

Figure 6 illustrates the throughput performance comparison between Calico and Cilium in both intra-node and inter-node scenarios. The results demonstrate that Cilium consistently outperforms Calico in both intra-node and inter-node communication. Cilium achieves a significantly higher intra-node throughput of approximately 16 Gbps compared to Calico's 11 Gbps. Similarly, Cilium maintains a superior

inter-node throughput of around 5 Gbps, while Calico struggles to reach 3 Gbps. These findings suggest that Cilium's architecture and implementation offer significant advantages in terms of network performance and scalability.

Figure 6. Throughput of Calico vs Cilium

Figure 7. Calico Policy Implementation

Calico on an OpenStack testbed was used to do the testing in a controlled setting. The traffic control (TC) hooks in both Cilium and Calico connect BPF programs at the pod's veth interface entrance and exit. Next, OpenStack virtual machines were used to conduct host mode benchmarks of Calico and Cilium e-BPF. Figure 7 shows that there are still significant

overheads in the K8s design, namely in inter-node communication and in CNI plugins, even if the e-BPF data plane is an improvement. Additionally, in the inter-node situation, Calico e-BPF performs better than Cilium. Calico offers a pure Layer 3 network solution with minimum overheads by using Linux kernel routing capabilities on each node, in contrast to

Cilium's tunnelling mode and encapsulation header requirements. All other performance assessments in this paper were conducted using Calico e-BPF. Repeating Calico and host intra-node testing on bare-metal yielded host latency and throughput that were 8.7% and 10.7% quicker, respectively, than OpenStack's 33% and 31% values. The fact that OpenStack is under more stress suggests that the network configurations of the VM and its modules, which use CNI, are not complementary.

Literature Review

This section contains a literature study with the objective of improving the performance of the Kubernetes network. It provides a detailed account of numerous research that focuses on container network interfaces and system tuning. Within this section, Table 1 (Appendix) is shown that provides a summary of the several literature reviews that have been covered.

In this paper, Dakic et al. (2024) stress the importance of consistently and accurately evaluating Kubernetes CNIs to guarantee that HPC workloads can run to their maximum capacity. Due to their inefficiency and error-prone nature, traditional manual approaches to assessing network latency and bandwidth are not suitable for the demanding requirements of HPC systems. The suggested solution employs Ansible to automate and standardize the evaluation process for various CNIs, performance profiles, and settings, therefore resolving the issue. They developed several Ansible playbooks to simplify the deployment, configuration, and execution of CNIs and evaluations; this will ensure that Kubernetes-based infrastructures can manage the rigorous performance requirements of HPC applications. Inadequate network setups should not cripple HPC workloads, so this method is crucial for protecting their performance integrity (Dakic, et al., 2024).

This research, Kang et al. (2021) gives experimental findings on the performance of containerized DDS applications in terms of virtualization overhead, security, transport

protocols (UDP unicast and multicast), dependability (DDS Reliable and Best-Effort QoS), and more. Distributed cloud applications are managed and scaled with Kubernetes (K8s), the de facto standard for container orchestration. Second, hundreds of mission-critical systems throughout the world employ OMG's DDS, which is a standardized, data-centric, peer-to-peer publish/subscribe middleware. It is uncertain how network virtualization affects the performance of DDS applications, and it is also questionable if DDS programs can be executed in K8s for latency-sensitive edge computing. This study examines the performance overhead of Flannel, Weave-Net, and Kuber-router plugins on a mixed ARM+AMD K8s cluster (Kang, et al., 2021).

This study, Koukis et al. (2024) evaluates the performance, both qualitatively and quantitatively, of several CNI plugins in K8s environments, including implementations of the lightweight Edge. They tested two scenarios (intra- and inter-host) and found intriguing insights and tradeoffs for researchers and practitioners. For instance, plugins in lightweight distributions may not enhance CPU/memory or throughput, but they do improve lifecycle metrics like pod readiness times. Kubernetes (K8s) is a mature orchestration solution for cloud and edge containerized application deployment and management. Kubernetes networking must be optimized for high-performance connection and low resource use to be useful at the edge (Koukis, et al., 2024).

This study, Kapočius (2020) compares nine major CNI plugins' TCP and HTTP performance in VMware ESXi and real data centers. Results guide CNI plugin selection for virtualized or real data centers. Containerization and microservices architecture are gaining popularity in ICT. Container deployment occurs in public and private cloud environments, typically in VM settings for flexibility. Microservices require a lot of containers, hence Kubernetes is a popular alternative. Kubernetes relies on CNI (Container Networking Interface) and plugins for networking solutions. To choose the best plugin, examine its performance (Kapočius, 2020).

The study, Kumar and Trivedi (2020) put details of Kubernetes networking and internal communication. They looked at Kubernetes networking features including pods, deployment, services, ingress, plugins for networks, multi-host communication, and CNI plugins. Kubernetes network plugin (CNI) benchmark results were also compared on a 10 Gbit/s network. Recently, containerization has outperformed virtualization for large-scale application deployment. Containers run applications with all libraries and dependencies in a tiny space. When it comes to orchestrating, deploying, configuring, scaling, and load-balancing containers, Kubernetes is essential. Kubernetes networking enables the virtualization of containers (Kumar, & Trivedi, 2020).

In this research, Sittenauer, Krcmar and Kroß (2021) evaluate Flannel and Calico CNI plugin network performance in Kubernetes and Rancher K3s cloud and IoT-like settings. Latency and bandwidth evaluate performance. CPU and memory utilization are monitored during network testing. They compare measurements to find the best cloud and edge setup. The Internet of Things has dramatically boosted Internet-connected devices. Edge Computing simplifies and speeds cloud data exchange by bringing data sources closer to IoT devices. Low-latency IoT applications like automotive require network performance. Containers have transformed cloud application deployment and management by replacing virtual machines. Virtual machines consume more resources than containers, which launch in seconds. Kubernetes has been deployed in Edge Computing environments with unified management platforms in recent study (Sittenauer, Krcmar, & Kroß, 2021).

Conclusion and Future Work

Rapid advancements in big data and cloud computing have led to Kubernetes' rise to prominence as the leading container orchestration technology. Kubernetes networking performance optimization continues to be a key challenge despite the fact that it is

flexible and efficient in managing containerized workloads across a variety of infrastructures. CNIs, which are short for container network interfaces, are essential to the performance of the platform since they make it possible for pods and nodes to communicate with one another. Optimizing Kubernetes network performance is critical for deploying scalable and efficient containerized applications. This study highlights the strengths and limitations of key CNI plugins, including Flannel, Cilium, Calico, and Antrea, in terms of throughput, security, and usability. Flannel excels in simplicity for small to medium-sized clusters, while Cilium and Calico offer robust security and scalability features for complex workloads. Antrea balances performance and flexibility, making it suitable for modern microservices architectures. System tuning profiles further enhance Kubernetes' capabilities, enabling seamless integration of CNIs with efficient resource utilization. The insights provided serve as a comprehensive guide for selecting the most appropriate CNI and tuning configuration to meet diverse deployment needs, ensuring optimal performance for Kubernetes environment.

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Appendix

Table 1. Summary of the Literature Review for Kubernetes Network Performance: Evaluating CNIs and System Tuning Profiles

Study	Focus Area	Key Contributions	Evaluation Metrics/Methods	Tools /Technologies	Challenges	Future Recommendations
Dacic, et al., (2024)	Automated evaluation of Kubernetes CNIs for HPC workloads	Introduced Ansible-based automation for evaluating network bandwidth and latency across CNIs to ensure reliable performance assessments	Bandwidth, latency, and replicability	Kubernetes, CNIs, Ansible	Manual CNI evaluation processes are error-prone and time-consuming	Expand automation to include fault tolerance testing and support for emerging CNIs.
Kang, et al., (2021)	Performance of containerized DDS applications in K8s for IoT	Examined virtualisation overhead, QoS, transport mechanisms, and network plugins for DDS in edge/cloud setups	Latency, reliability (QoS), transport mechanism (UDP unicast/multicast)	Kubernetes (K8s), Flannel, Weave-Net, Kuber-router, DDS middleware	Balancing latency-sensitive performance with reliability under virtualisation overhead	Explore adaptive CNI configurations for real-time QoS adjustments and hybrid edge-cloud setups.
Koukis, et al., (2024)	Performance evaluation of CNI plugins in lightweight K8s for edge applications	Compared CNI performance (e.g., pod readiness times, CPU/memory, throughput) in intra- and inter-host scenarios in lightweight Kubernetes setups	Lifecycle metrics, throughput, CPU/memory usage	Kubernetes, various CNIs	Limited improvement in resource consumption despite optimizations in lightweight setups	Research advanced CNIs designed specifically for constrained edge environments.
Kapočius, (2020)	TCP and HTTP performance comparison of nine major CNIs in VMware ESXi and real data centers	Provided comparative performance insights for choosing CNIs in virtualised and real data centre settings	TCP, HTTP performance	VMware ESXi, Kubernetes, CNIs	Complexities in achieving consistent network performance across diverse CNI plugins	Standardise benchmarking frameworks for multi-environment CNI comparisons.
Kumar, & Trivedi, (2020)	Kubernetes networking and internal communication, focusing on 10 Gbps environments	Explored Kubernetes networking aspects, including CNIs, multi-host communication, and network plugins, along with benchmark comparisons	Bandwidth, throughput, fault tolerance	Kubernetes, CNIs	Difficulty in optimizing CNIs for ultra-high-speed (10 Gbps) networks in distributed applications	Investigate next-gen CNIs capable of leveraging higher bandwidth environments more effectively.
Sittenauer, Krcmar, & Kroß, (2021)	Flannel and Calico CNI performance evaluation in cloud and IoT-like edge settings	Analysed latency, bandwidth, CPU, and memory utilization for Flannel and Calico in K8s and Rancher K3s setups	Latency, bandwidth, CPU/memory utilization	Kubernetes (K8s), Rancher K3s, Flannel, Calico	Variability in performance between cloud and edge deployments with identical configurations	Develop hybrid CNIs optimized for seamless transitions between edge and cloud environments.